

TITLE:

**IMPAIRED BETA CELL SIGNALING IS PRESENT IN NON DIABETIC
RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS PATIENTS**

Ferraz-Amaro I¹, Hernández-Hernández V¹, Delgado-Frías E¹, Gantes MA¹, García-Dopico JA², Medina-Vega L², González-Gay MA³, Díaz-González F¹.

¹Servicio de Reumatología. Hospital Universitario de Canarias. Tenerife. Spain.

²Servicio de Laboratorio. Hospital Universitario de Canarias. Tenerife. Spain

³Servicio de Reumatología. Hospital Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla. Santander. Spain.

Hernández-Hernández V: mvhhernandez@yahoo.es

Delgado-Frías E: super_esmely@hotmail.com

Gantes MA: gantesmar@hotmail.com

García-Dopico JA: jagdopico@mac.com

Medina-Vega L: lilianmedinatfe@hotmail.com

González-Gay MA: miguelaggay@hotmail.com

Díaz-González F: Federico.diaz.gonzalez@gmail.com

Short-Running title: Impaired beta cell signaling & rheumatoid arthritis

Corresponding author:

Ivan Ferraz-Amaro. Servicio de Reumatología.

Hospital Universitario de Canarias. Ofra s/n. La Cuesta.

38320 Santa Cruz de Tenerife. Spain.

Phone: +34922678502. Fax: +34922646792. Email: iferrazamaro@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Introduction. To investigate how markers of beta cell secretion (proinsulin processing metabolites) are expressed in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patients and its potential relationship with the insulin resistance (IR) observed in these patients.

Methods. 101 RA patients and 99 non-diabetic sex and age-matched controls were included. IR by homeostatic model assessment (HOMA2), and beta cell secretion through insulin, split and intact proinsulin, and C-peptide were assessed in both groups. We performed multiple regression analysis to compare IR between groups and to explore the relation between RA features, proinsulin metabolites and IR. Data were adjusted for glucocorticoids intake and for IR classical risk factors.

Results. RA patients compared to controls showed higher HOMA-IR (beta coef., 0.40 [95%CI 0.20-0.59], $p=0.00$). When data were adjusted for glucocorticoids intake, non-on corticosteroid patients maintained a higher IR index (beta 0.14 [0.05-0.24], $p=0.00$). Impaired features of insulin processing in RA patients were detected through elevated split proinsulin levels (beta 0.70 p/molL [0.38-1.02], $p=0.00$). This data was also significant when adjusted for prednisone intake (beta 0.19 [0.00-0.36], $p=0.04$). Split proinsulin to C-peptide ratios were higher in RA patients undergoing corticosteroid therapy (beta 0.25 pmol/L [0.12-0.38] $p=0.03$) and almost significant in the comparison between non-on corticoids patients and controls (beta 0.16 pmol/L [-0.02-0.34], $p=0.08$). Interestingly, the impact of HOMA-IR on intact proinsulin to C-peptide ratio was higher in controls when compared to patients (beta 6.23 [1.41-11.06] vs. 0.43 [-0.86-1.71], $p=0.03$).

Conclusion. Beta cell signaling is impaired in non-diabetic and non-on corticoids RA patients by a mechanism that seems to be, at least in part, independent of IR.

Keywords: rheumatoid arthritis, insulin resistance, proinsulin, insulin resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, systemic, inflammatory disorder of unknown etiology that if uncontrolled may lead to destruction and deformity of joints due to erosion of cartilage and bone. Although a higher prevalence of traditional cardiovascular risk factors may be present in patients with RA than in the general population, epidemiologic data suggest that RA is an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease and this may be a major contributor to increased mortality among patients [1, 2]. Several reports have linked clinical RA activity with a reduction in peripheral insulin sensitivity [3-7].

Insulin resistance (IR) refers to a state in which a given concentration of insulin is associated with a subnormal glucose response[8]. IR is the key primary defect underlying the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus and is a central component defining the metabolic syndrome, a constellation of abnormalities including obesity, hypertension, glucose intolerance, and dyslipidemia that eventually may lead to cardiovascular disease. IR has been defined in the last decade as being frequently associated with a state of low-grade inflammation, and therefore it is assumed that inflammation might contribute in a major way to its development [9]. Similarly, IR is now also recognized as a component of several disorders in which chronic inflammatory state is present such as RA.

A complex network of inflammatory cytokines, adipocytokines, transcription factors, receptor molecules, and acute-phase reactants are involved in the development of IR. Both peripheral insulin action and insulin secretion has been shown to be impaired in IR states leading to an increased proportion of insulin that is proinsulin[10]. These findings are supported by the fact that intermediate proinsulin products like des-31,32 or des-

62,64 proinsulin are elevated in IR and diabetes [11, 12] showing that the processing of proinsulin to insulin in the beta cells is impaired.

Previous studies that have examined insulin sensitivity and β -cell function in patients with RA have relied solely on fasting parameters, that is, HOMA-IR and HOMA%B (Homeostatic Model Assessment). Although these model-derived indices are well validated, they provide no information about proinsulin processing or insulin secretion by beta cells. In this regard, disproportionate hyperproinsulinemia as an indicator of β -cell dysfunction have not been explored in RA. The aim of this study was to investigate beta cell function (secretion) in RA patients and its potential relationship with the IR observed in these patients.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Study participants. Two hundred subjects, 101 RA patients and 99 age and sex-matched controls were recruited for this cross-sectional study. RA patients were men or women ages 18 or older diagnosed by a rheumatologist as having fulfilled 2010 ACR/EULAR diagnostic criteria [13]. For inclusion in the present study, RA disease duration was required to be ≥ 1 year. To minimize the potential effects of TNF-blockers on IR[5], RA patients undergoing TNF-antagonist therapy were not included in the present study. However, since corticosteroids are often used in the management of RA, patients taking prednisone or equivalent dose (12 mg/day or less) were not excluded. Nevertheless, we established two groups within the cohort of RA patients; those on prednisone therapy that encompassed patients on current treatment with these drugs or who had been taken corticosteroids within three months before the onset of the study, and those not taking corticosteroids that included RA patients that had not received corticosteroids over the last 12 months prior to the recruitment. Glucocorticoid dose was measured as the equivalent for prednisone in mg/day/previous three months dose. Patients and controls with diabetes mellitus were not included in the study. Therefore, none of the patients or controls was on glucose-lowering drugs or insulin therapy. All patients and controls had a glucemia < 7 mmol/l. Patients and controls were excluded if they had a history of myocardial infarction, angina, stroke, glomerular filtration rate less than 60 mL/min/1.73m², history of cancer, or any other chronic disease or evidence of infection. None of the controls was on corticosteroid treatment. The study protocol was approved by the institutional review committee at Hospital Universitario de Canarias (Spain), and all subjects provided written informed consent.

Data collection. Study participation for subjects in both the RA and controls patients was identical, except that subjects with RA were asked additional questions pertaining

to their disease. Subjects completed a cardiovascular risk factor and medication usage questionnaire and underwent a physical examination to assess anthropometrics measures and blood pressure. Medical records were reviewed to ascertain diagnosis and medication. Weight was assessed to the nearest 100 g with the participant standing on a portable digital scale (SECA, Hamburg, Germany). Standing height was measured to the nearest 1 cm with a stadiometer (SECA). The waist circumference was measured at the smallest circumference between the rib cage and the iliac crest, with the subject in the standing position. The hip circumference was measured at the widest circumference between the waist and the thighs. The waist-to-hip ratio was estimated. In patients with RA, disease activity was measured using the Disease Activity Score (DAS28) in 28 joints[14], and disease disability through Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ)[15]. Metabolic syndrome was defined through 2005 National Cholesterol Education Program (Adult Treatment Panel [ATP] III) criteria) [16].

Assessments. Homeostatic model assessment (HOMA) method was performed to determine IR. Briefly, the HOMA model is used to yield an estimate of insulin sensitivity (%S) and β -cell function (%B) from fasting plasma insulin (or C-peptide) and glucose concentrations. In this study we have used HOMA2: the updated-computer HOMA model[17]. This model can be used to determine insulin sensitivity and β -cell function from paired fasting plasma glucose and specific insulin, or C-peptide, concentrations across a range of 1–2,200 pmol/l for insulin and 1–25 mmol/l for glucose. In our study we have use C-peptide to calculate β -cell function since C-peptide is a marker of secretion; and insulin data to calculate %S (since HOMA-%S is derived from glucose disposal as a function of insulin concentration). The computer model gives a value for insulin sensitivity expressed as HOMA2-%S (where 100% is normal). HOMA2-IR (insulin resistance index) is simply the reciprocal of %S.

Insulin (Architect Abbott, 2000I) and C-peptide (Immulite 2000, Siemens) were determined by chemiluminescent immunometric assays. Intact proinsulin was assessed through ELISA (Millipore, Billerica, MA). This ELISA does not cross-react with human insulin and the presence of insulin (up to 208 μ U/ml) in serum does not interfere with the assay result. The kit has no cross-reactivity with the major species of proinsulin metabolites des(31,32) proinsulin while cross-reacts only weakly with the minor intermediate des(64,65) proinsulin (inter-assay precision: 3.3–9.0 %; intra-assay: 0.4–7.7). Total (split) proinsulin was detected by ELISA (Millipore, Billerica, MA). This kit has 100% cross reactivity to intact human proinsulin and its major processed intermediate, des(31,32) proinsulin, and 81% cross reactivity to its processed intermediate des(64,65) proinsulin. Human Insulin (up to 200 μ U/mL) and Human C-Peptide (up to 10ng/mL) do not interfere with the assay result. Precision was estimated as inter-assay: 2.9–8.3 %; intra-assay: 0.8–8.5%. Split proinsulin to C-peptide ratio was used as a surrogate marker of β -cell function[18]. Standard techniques were used to measure plasma glucose, C-reactive protein (CRP), the Westergren erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and serum lipids.

Statistical analysis. On the basis of previous findings [12, 18] we assumed a normal intact proinsulin to C-peptide ratio to be 10 % in controls and 14 % in patients with insulin resistance (diabetics patients in the reference). With these assumptions, in a 1:1 relation, and according to a T student test with an alpha level of 0.05 and a beta level of 0.15, we estimated that we would need to enroll 184 patients, 92 patients and 92 controls. Demographic and clinical characteristics shown in table 1 were compared between patients with RA and controls using chi-square tests for categorical variables or T-Student test for continuous variables (data described as mean \pm standard deviation). For non-continuous variables U-Mann-Whitney test was performed or logarithmic

transformation was made and data were expressed as median (interquartile range). Association of insulin sensitivity and beta-cell function with clinical features of RA as well as comparisons between RA patients and controls were performed through multivariate analysis adjusting for factors known to be associated with IR. Two different models were defined for the results obtained from these analyses. An unadjusted model where RA features and metabolic syndrome factors were associated through univariate analysis, and an adjusted model where RA features were correlated with insulin sensitivity parameters after adjustment for these classical risk factors through multiple regression. Dissimilar impact of HOMA-IR on proinsulin metabolites in patients and controls was established adding an interaction term using multivariate regression analysis. All analyses used a 5% 2-sided significance level and were performed using SPSS software, version 19 (IBM, Chicago, Illinois, USA). A p value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Characteristics of the participants

A total of 200 participants, 101 RA patients and 99 controls, with a mean (\pm standard deviation) age of 55.2 ± 10.0 and 55.1 ± 10.6 ($p=0.90$) years respectively were included in this study. The demographic and disease-related characteristics among the participants are shown in Table 1. Patients in our series had a moderate-active disease as illustrated through DAS28 (3.99 ± 1.41). Half of them (54.5%) were on prednisone (in an average 6.2 ± 2.5 mg day/last year doses). There were no differences between patients and controls in regard to BMI, waist circumference and presence of hypertension, or metabolic syndrome. As expected, analyses of ESR and CRP values disclosed statistically significant differences between controls and patients. Apart from an increased frequency of positive rheumatoid factor among RA patients on corticosteroid therapy compared to those not taking corticosteroids (78% *versus* 38%, $p=0.00$), no significant differences between both subgroups of RA patients were observed in terms of disease duration, activity scores, age or BMI.

<insert table 1 here>

Insulin resistance indexes

Insulin resistance indexes are illustrated in table 2. RA patients showed a higher HOMA-IR index (*log* beta coefficient, 0.40 [95% CI 0.20-0.59], $p=0.00$) and an elevated beta cell function -HOMA%B- (*log* beta coef. 22% [95% CI 5-39], $p=0.01$) respect to controls. When RA patients were divided in prednisone intake or not, non-on corticoids RA patients showed a statistically significant higher IR respect to controls (*log* beta coef. 0.14 [0.05-0.24], $p=0.00$). Similar results were found regard β -cell

function, with an elevated HOMA%B in non-on corticoids patients when compared to controls (*log* beta coef. 11 % [95% CI 2-19], $p=0.02$).

As shown in Table 2, in the multiple regression analysis none of the IR indexes (%B and IR indexes, data for %S were not showed because it represents simply the reciprocal of IR) were correlated with RA features like disease duration, rheumatoid factor positivity, ESR, C-reactive protein, DAS 28 or HAQ scores, mg/day/previous 3 months prednisone doses, current prednisone or DMARD intake. This absence of association remained non-significant when data were adjusted for classical risk factors involved in IR such us sex, age, BMI, or hypertension (adjusted model). Only C-reactive protein was inversely related with IR ($p=0.05$) but this association was not maintained when adjusted for classical risk factors for IR .

<insert table 2 here>

As is disclosed in table 2, classical IR triggers (BMI, waist circumference and hypertension) were strongly associated with IR indexes in RA patients but dissimilar impact of these classical risk factors on IR indexes in patients and controls were found. In both RA and control groups, higher BMI, waist circumference, presence of hypertension and male sex were each associated generally with worse IR indexes (data not showed). However, the impact of BMI on IR index in RA patients was more important than in controls (beta coefficient 0.06 [0.03-0.10] for RA patients, vs. 0.03 [0.01-0.05] in controls, $p=0.00$). Contrary, waist circumference's impact seemed to be more important in controls (beta coef. 0.03 [0.01-0.04] vs. 0.02 [0.01-0.03], $p=0.05$) although statistic significance was not reached.

β -cell function markers and proinsulin processing metabolites

Independent of prednisone intake, C-peptide levels were higher in non-on steroids patients when compared to controls, (*log*C-peptide, beta coef. 0.20 nmol/L [0.02-0.38], $p=0.03$). Insulin levels were also higher in non-on corticoids RA patients and in those taking steroids. In the other hand, neither insulin nor C-peptide correlated with prednisone mg/day/3 previous months.

Markers of beta cell dysfunction were different between controls and patients (figure 1). In this regard, split proinsulin, that expresses intact human proinsulin plus its major intermediate metabolites des(31,32) proinsulin, and des(64,65) proinsulin, was higher in RA patients, (*log*Split insulin, beta coef. 0.70 pmol/L [0.38-1.02], $p=0.00$), even when adjusting for corticosteroid intake, sex, BMI, and age. Split proinsulin to C-peptide ratio was higher in RA patients undergoing corticosteroid therapy (beta coef. 0.25 pmol/L [0.12-0.38] $p=0.03$) and almost significant in the comparison between non-on corticoids patients and controls (beta coef. 0.16 pmol/L [-0.02-0.34] $p=0.08$). Figure 1 illustrates these differences.

Intact proinsulin showed similar results. Generally, patients expressed higher levels (beta coef. 0.81 pmol/L [0.13-1.46] $p=0.02$) and this data remained significant when data was adjusted for corticoids intake (table 3). Intact proinsulin to C-peptide ratio was higher in patients when compared to controls (beta coef. 0.55 pmol/L [0.05-1.05] $p=0.03$). When this data was adjusted for steroids consumption, statically significance was not reached but patients showed superior ratios.

RA features like ESR, CRP, DAS28, HAQ or rheumatoid factor positivity were not associated with beta cell markers or proinsulin processing metabolites (table 3). Only disease duration showed a significant negative association with split proinsulin and split proinsulin to C-peptide ratios. Similarly, current prednisone intake (as dichotomous variable) was associated was higher split insulin to C-peptide ratio.

Different relation between HOMA-IR and proinsulin metabolites was found in patients when compared to controls. Table 4 shows that generally controls expressed higher beta coefficients of proinsulin metabolites for a same increase in IR index. Thus, the impact of IR on intact proinsulin to C-peptide ratio was higher in controls than in RA patients (6.23 [95%CI 1.41-11.06] vs 0.43 [-0.86-1.71], $p=0.03$); this association was not found for split proinsulin/C-peptide ratio. When patients were divided in those taking corticoids and those that do not, no differences were found in the relation between HOMA-IR and split or intact proinsulin (Table 4).

<insert table 4 here>

<insert figure 1 here>

DISCUSSION

Insulin resistance is characterized by hyperglycemia and relative impairment in insulin secretion. Understanding its pathogenesis is complicated because patients present with a combination of varying degrees of both peripheral resistance and insulin deficiency.

HOMA indexes, although widespread used, do not account for these differences between hepatic and peripheral insulin sensitivity, increases or decreases in insulin secretion, or the contribution of circulating proinsulin. For this reason, we decided to evaluate RA related IR in a more accurate way by measuring intact proinsulin and its metabolites as an expression of the synthesis and secretion of insulin. Our study suggests that the processing of proinsulin to insulin in the beta cells is impaired in non-diabetic non-on corticoids RA patients. To our knowledge, this is the first study that has examined insulin resistance in RA with regard to these insulin processing metabolites.

Insulin production in normal subjects involves cleavage of insulin from proinsulin; 10 to 15 percent of secreted insulin is proinsulin and its conversion intermediates. In contrast, the proportion of immunoreactive insulin that is proinsulin in type 2 diabetes is increased considerably in the basal state[11]. Proinsulin levels have been shown to be related to coronary heart disease[19] and to be a strong predictor of incident type 2 diabetes mellitus [18]. In our study we have found an increase in intact and split proinsulin when RA patients were compared to controls and this difference was not corticoid mediated. The reasons for the presence of increased levels of proinsulin metabolites in RA patients are likely to be multifactorial and remain unknown. The matter of fact, studies linking insulin propeptides and inflammation are lacking. It is possible that the cause of the disproportional hyperproinsulinaemia found in RA patients from our study may arise from inefficient proinsulin processing within the beta cell secretory granule or the premature release of proinsulin as a result of increased

demand for insulin as observed in insulin-resistant states[20]. Elevations in the ratio of proinsulin to insulin as well as absolute proinsulin concentrations adjusted for fasting insulin have been proposed as early markers of beta cell dysfunction[21] but proinsulin-to-C-peptide ratios have been shown to be a stronger predictor of diabetes[18]. These findings support the use of C-peptide as the denominator for proinsulin ratios, to more accurately reflect the degree of disproportional hyperproinsulinaemia and is in agreement with our findings that show higher and significant split proinsulin to C-peptide ratios in patients when compared to controls.

It is difficult to separate IR that occurs peripherally, that the one that occurs because or after the beta cell damage. It is unknown whether beta cell failure is first and then compensatory mechanisms occur, or if instead, once the resistance to insulin action in peripheral organs takes place, then pancreatic cell damage occurs. In our study we have found, that for a same rise in IR, proinsulin levels increase higher in controls. This could denote that beta cell damage in RA patients is independent of peripheral IR. That is, inflammation, or the disease it self, lead to a beta cell dysfunction directly, that at least could be partly independent of the IR. Our data regarding IR indexes are in agreement with previous studies [4, 6, 22-26] that show that abnormalities in glucose metabolism with a pattern of IR are present in RA, but, as stated, these studies have always used fasting HOMA derived devices. Unlike previous studies [22, 24, 27] we have not found association between disease activity scores, ESR and CRP and IR in our series of RA patients.

In the multiple regression analysis models we have found than abdominal obesity and BMI correlate with IR indexes in RA patients (and controls). This finding is in agreement with the knowledge that waist circumference and adiposity are the main contributors to IR in the general population. Abnormal body composition is a feature

observed in RA, and the amount and distribution of fat and lean mass have important implications in IR[28]. Interestingly, according to our results, it seems that the BMI impact on IR is higher in RA patients than in controls.

Several mechanisms may account for the development of hyperglycemia in corticoids-treated individuals including increased hepatic gluconeogenesis, inhibition of glucose uptake in adipose tissue, and alteration of receptor and post-receptor functions[29].

Because glucocorticoids are an important issue regarding this and they are usually prescribed in RA, doses and corticosteroid intake were considered in our study and patients were divided in those taking and not taking steroids. In this regard, following multiple regression analysis, we observed that prednisone intake (as dichotomic variable) or average prednisone mg/day/3 previous months were not associated with IR indexes in the intragroup RA patients comparison except for the relation with C-peptide and split proinsulin. Because of that, our data are in keeping with previous findings that support the notion that the use of high-dose glucocorticoids often results in hyperglycemia. However, it may not be always the case in RA as Dessein et al illustrated that a low cumulative corticosteroid dose in RA patients may lead to improvement in beta cell function as estimated by HOMA-%B [24]. In any case, the mechanisms associated with the development of metabolic syndrome related to corticosteroid use in RA need further elucidation. In this regard, unlike we might expect, Toms et al [30] did not find association between corticosteroid use and metabolic syndrome in RA .

We acknowledge some limitations in our study. Both patients and controls exhibited high BMI, nearly in the obese range. Although this potential confounding effect was corrected in the multivariate analysis perhaps the ideal comparison would have been with controls in a normal weight situation and, because of this, possibly IR indexes and

proinsulin levels could have been overestimated in controls. However, RA is a disease that is frequently associated to changes in BMI and situations of high BMI are frequently observed in patients with this condition. Secondly, as discussed above, corticosteroids exert pleiotropic metabolic effects that may be difficult to be understood in the setting of a chronic inflammatory disease like RA. This may be considered like double-edged sword as they have been associated with IR but at the same time they also have an anti-inflammatory effects.

In conclusion, in the present study we observed that intermediate proinsulin and insulin metabolites processing are impaired in RA. The mechanisms leading to this fact may be related to the disease itself and they may be different from those occurring in the setting of other IR related conditions such as diabetes mellitus or obesity.

This investigation was performed with a research fund to I. Ferraz-Amaro from Fundación Española de Reumatología.

LIST OF ABREBIATIONS

IR, Insulin Resistance

RA, Rheumatoid Arthritis

HOMA, Homeostatic Model Assessment

DAS28, Disease Activity Score

HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire

TNF, Tumor Necrosis Factor

ELISA, Enzyme Linked ImmunoSorbent Assay

CRP, C-reactive Protein

ESR, Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate

DMARD, Desease-Modifying Antirheumatic Drug

BMI, Body Mass Index

GC, Glucocorticoids

RF, Rheumatoid Factor

HDL, High Density Lipoprotein

LDL, Low densitiy lipoprotein

Competing interests

No competing interest are declare by the authors

Authors' information

IFA and FDG designed the study and wrote the manuscript. VHH, EDF and MG monitored patients. JGD and LMV performed the laboratories studies. MAGG supported the design and revised the article.

Table 1. Demographics and disease-related characteristics of patients and controls.

	<i>Rheumatoid arthritis (n=101)</i>			<i>p</i> †	<i>Controls (n=99)</i>	<i>p</i> *
		<i>GC-RA (n=46)</i>	<i>GC+RA (55)</i>			
Age. years	55.2 ± 10.0	53.0 ± 10.1	57.1 ± 9.7	0.04 *	55.1 ± 10.6	0.90
Female. n(%)	86 (85)	38 (67)	48 (87)	0.51	90 (91)	0.21
Body mass index. kg/m ²	29.5 ± 5.9	27.8 ± 4.8	30.0 ± 6.6	0.18	29.5 ± 5.4	0.59
Hip circumference. cm	106 (99-118)	105 (97-115)	109 (99-118)	0.17	102 (98-110)	0.23
Waist circumference male, cm	106 ± 17	105 ± 12	107 ± 22	0.79	100 ± 12	0.57
Waist circumference female. cm	96 ± 15	92 ± 14	98 ± 15	0.13	91 ± 11	0.12
Waist to hip ratio	0.90 (0.85-0.94)	0.89 (0.83-0.94)	0.90 (0.86-0.94)	0.34	0.86 (0.80-0.92)	0.71
Hypertension. n(%)	36 (38)	14 (25)	22 (40)	0.51	31 (31)	0.34
Statins intake. n(%)	29 (30)	13 (23)	16 (29)	0.78	28 (28)	0.77
Metabolic syndromme. n(%)	32 (37)	15 (27)	17 (31)	0.96	18 (18)	0.11
ESR. mm/hour	25 (16-39)	25(15-41)	26 (18-39)	0.70	18 (13-25)	0.00 *
CRP. mg/dL	3.8 (1.4-9.4)	4.5 (1.3-13.7)	3.2 (1.6-9.0)	0.59	2.0 (0.9-4.7)	0.00 *
Cholesterol. mg/dL	210 ± 40	203 ± 30	216 ± 46	0.18	207 ± 39	0.62
Triglycerides. mg/dL	118 (85-151)	110 (81-139)	121 (91-152)	0.28	102 (69-133)	0.00 *
HDL cholesterol. mg/dL	59 ± 15	58 ± 14	60 ± 16	0.48	56 ± 14	0.13
LDL cholesterol. mg/dL	127 ± 33	127 ± 28	127 ± 37	0.89	129 ± 34	0.62
Disease duration. years	7.5 ± 5.8	8.7 ± 4.5	6.2± 6.8	0.08		
DAS28-ESR	3.99 ± 1.41	4.11 ± 1.56	3.18 ± 1.27	0.45		
HAQ	0.61 (0.24-1.28)	0.69 (0.13-1.37)	0.55 (0.2-1.23)	0.92		
Positive rheumatoid factor. n(%)	64 (65)	21 (38)	43 (78)	0.00 *		
Current non biologic DMARD. n(%)	88(87)	41 (73)	47 (85)	0.58		
Current prednisone. n(%)	55 (54.5)					
Prednisone. average mg/day/3 months	6.24 ± 2.54					

GC-RA represents RA patients non on corticosteroids; GC+RA denotes RA patients taking prednisone

p* refers to the comparison between controls and patients. p† for the comparison between non on corticoids and on corticoides patients

Data expressed as mean (± standard deviation) or median (interquartile range). Dicothomus variables are expressed as *n* and percentage. * denotes p value < 0.05.

ESR=erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP=C reactive protein; HAQ=Health Assessment Questionnaire; DAS28=Disease Activity Score; HDL=High density lipoprotein; LDL=Low densitiy lipoprotein.

DMARD=Disease-modifying Antirheumatic Drug

Table 2. Association of classical risk factors and RA characteristics with insulin sensitivity and β -cell function in patients and controls

	RA and controls (n=200)		RA patients (101)			
			Unadjusted model		Adjusted model	
	β coefficient (95% CI)	p	β coefficient (95% CI)	p	β coefficient (95% CI)	p
Insulin Resistance (<i>logHOMA-IR</i>)						
RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=101 and controls=99)	0.40 (0.20-0.59)	0.00				
GC-RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=56 and controls=99)	0.14 (0.05-0.24)	0.00				
GC+RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=55 and controls=99)	0.17 (0.10-0.24)	0.00				
RA features						
Disease duration			-0.02 (-0.06-0.01)	0.19	-0.01 (-0.05-0.03)	0.59
RF positivity			0.00 (-0.39-0.39)	0.99	-0.15 (-0.54-0.24)	0.86
ESR			-0.00 (-0.01-0.01)	0.66	-0.01 (-0.02-0.00)	0.26
CRP			-0.01 (-0.02-0.00)	0.05	-0.01 (-0.02-0.00)	0.07
Current prednisone			0.23 (-0.14-0.60)	0.22	0.04 (-0.32-0.40)	0.81
Prednisone, mg/day/previous 3 months			0.01 (-0.18-0.20)	0.94	-0.23 (-0.46-0.01)	0.47
HAQ			-0.01 (-0.30-0.29)	0.97	0.12 (-0.18-0.41)	0.44
DAS28			-0.00 (-0.14-0.13)	0.95	-0.05 (-0.17-0.07)	0.40
Current non-biologic DMARD			-0.28 (-1.35-0.79)	0.60	0.08 (-0.67-0.82)	0.83
Classical IR risk factors						
Sex			-0.24 (-0.76-0.27)	0.35		
Age			0.00 (-0.02-0.02)	0.83		
BMI			0.06 (0.03-0.10)	0.00	*	
Waist circumference			0.02 (0.01-0.03)	0.00	*	
Triglycerides			0.00 (0.00-0.01)	0.07		
Hypertension			0.48 (0.11-0.86)	0.01	*	
β-cell function (<i>logHOMA%B</i>)						
RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=101 and controls=99)	22 (5-39)	0.01				
GC-RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=56 and controls=99)	11 (2-19)	0.02				
GC+RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=55 and controls=99)	8 (0-15)	0.05				
RA features						
Disease duration			2 (-1-4)	0.27	1 (-2-4)	0.40

RF positivity	10 (21-42)	0.52	11 (-19-41)	0.46
ESR	0 (-1-1)	0.52	0 (-1-1)	0.61
CRP	1 (-2-1)	0.32	0 (-1-1)	0.40
Current prednisone	1 (-28-31)	0.93	3 (-26-32)	0.85
Prednisone, mg/day/previous 3 months	2 (-15-18)	0.83	10 (-8-21)	0.36
HAQ	-3 (-27-21)	0.83	3 (-20-26)	0.81
DAS28	-1 (-12-10)	0.81	-0 (-11-10)	0.95
Current non-biologic DMARD	-16 (110-79)	0.74	-15 (-100-71)	0.73
Classical IR risk factors				
Sex	-52 (-92--12)	0.01 *		
Age	-1 (-3-0)	0.06		
BMI	2 (-1-5)	0.16		
Waist circumference	0 (-1-1)	0.67		
Triglycerides	0 (-0-0)	0.90		
Hypertension	10 (-21-41)	0.53		

HOMA-IR and HOMA%B are considered dependent variables and were log transformed. Beta coefficients are expressed log transformed.

β coefficient refers to change in insulin resistance (IR) or beta cell function (%B) outcome per unit increase in the indicated characteristic.

'Sex' refers to the change from female to male; 'current prednisone' to the change from non corticoids to on corticosteroids treatment and 'RF positivity' to the change from negative to positive rheumatoid factor.

Adjusted model represents a model where RA features are adjusted for classical risk factors of previous model with $p < 0.20$ (BMI, and hypertension in IR model; and sex, age and BMI for %B model).

See table 1 for abbreviations and units.

Table 3. Associations of proinsulin processing metabolites with RA features.

Insulin and C-peptide (dependent variables)	β coefficient (95% CI)			
	<i>logInsulin pmol/L</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>logC-peptide</i>	<i>p</i>
RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=101 and controls=99)	0.39 (0.14-0.64)	0.00	0.61 (0.32-0.91)	0.00
GC-RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=56 and controls=99)	0.14 (0.01-0.27)	0.04	0.20 (0.02-0.38)	0.03
GC+RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=55 and controls=99)	0.15 (0.06-0.25)	0.00	0.29 (0.17-0.40)	0.00
RA patients features ((β 95% CI for RA=101)				
Disease duration	-0.79 (-3.32-1.74)	0.54	-0.01 (-0.02-0.00)	0.07
RF positivity	-10.9 (-46.9-25.2)	0.99	0.03 (-0.06-0.12)	0.51
ESR	-0.50 (-1.49-0.50)	0.33	-0.00 (-0.01-0.00)	0.12
CRP	-0.21 (-1.34-0.91)	0.03	0.00 (-0.00-0.00)	0.65
Current prednisone	0.13 (-0.23-0.48)	0.48	0.10 (0.01-0.18)	0.02
Prednisone. mg/day/previous 3 months	-3.28 (-22.36-15.80)	0.25	-0.02 (-0.05-0.02)	0.16
HAQ	3.03 (-20.32-26.37)	0.63	-0.02 (-0.09-0.05)	0.69
DAS28	-0.21 (-10.89-10.49)	0.67	0.00 (-0.03-0.03)	0.99
Current non-biologic DMARD	23.58 (-63.53-110.68)	0.79	0.05 (-0.13-0.23)	0.61
<i>logIntact proinsulin (dependent variable)</i>				
	<i>Intact proinsulin</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Intact proinsulin/ C-peptide ratio</i>	<i>p</i>
RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=101 and controls=99)	0.81 (0.13-1.46)	0.02	0.55 (0.05-1.05)	0.03
GC-RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=56 and controls=99)	0.34 (0.05-0.62)	0.02	1.65 (-0.06-3.35)	0.06
GC+RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=55 and controls=99)	0.24 (0.05-0.43)	0.01	0.14 (-0.04-0.33)	0.13
RA patients features ((β 95% CI for RA=101)				
Disease duration	0.03 (-0.46-0.51)	0.83	0.13 (-0.45-0.71)	0.96
RF positivity	3.4 (0.25-6.51)	0.11	3.45 (-0.34-7.25)	0.15
ESR	-0.03 (-0.12-0.06)	0.92	0.01 (-0.11-0.10)	0.62
CRP	0.02 (-0.07-0.12)	0.50	0.03 (-0.08-0.14)	0.47
Current prednisone	-0.07 (-0.73-0.59)	0.83	-1.40 (-5.30-2.50)	0.48
Prednisone. mg/day/previous 3 months	-0.11 (-1.86-1.65)	0.82	-0.05 (-1.83-1.73)	0.63
HAQ	0.62 (-2.13-3.37)	0.75	1.23 (-1.99-4.46)	0.85

DAS28	0.49 (-0.74-1.72)	0.65	0.39 (-1.03-1.82)	0.68
Current non-biologic DMARD	2.93 (-7.52-13.34)	0.91	3.40 (-7.45-14.26)	0.96
<i>logSplit proinsulin (dependent variable)</i>				
	<i>Split proinsulin</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Split proinsulin/ C-peptide ratio</i>	<i>p</i>
RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=101 and controls=99)	0.70 (0.38-1.02)	0.00	0.57 (0.30-0.88)	0.00
GC-RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=56 and controls=99)	0.19 (0.00-0.36)	0.04	0.16 (-0.02-0.34)	0.08
GC+RA vs controls (β 95% CI for RA=55 and controls=99)	0.33 (0.20-0.45)	0.00	0.25 (0.12-0.38)	0.00
RA patients features (β 95% CI for RA=101)				
Disease duration	-1.58 (-2.84--0.31)	0.01	-1.82 (-3.48--0.17)	0.02
RF positivity	2.83 (-8.33-13.98)	0.60	5.11 (-8.54-18.76)	0.67
ESR	0.08 (-0.39-0.22)	0.60	-0.02 (-0.39-0.35)	0.93
CRP	0.16 (-0.18-0.51)	0.42	0.20 (-0.23-0.62)	0.33
Current prednisone	0.57 (0.18-0.96)	0.00	0.41 (0.05-0.76)	0.03
Prednisone. mg/day/previous 3 months	-1.04 (-6.99-4.91)	0.98	-0.14 (-6.50-6.22)	0.71
HAQ	-3.17 (-11.15-4.81)	0.11	-0.35 (-10.84-10.14)	0.43
DAS28	1.11 (-2.89-5.11)	0.82	-1.79 (-3.01-6.67)	0.67
Current non-biologic DMARD	15.28 (-15.93-46.49)	0.83	15.43 (-17.36-48.23)	0.73

All β coefficients are adjusted for sex, age and body mass index. All dependent variables are considered log transformed.

Rheumatoid factor (RF) positivity, current prednisone and current non-biologic DMARD are considered dichotomous variables.

For abbreviations and units see table 1.

Table 4. Different relation between HOMA-IR index and proinsulin metabolites in controls and patients

	β coefficient (95%CI)			
	Intact proinsulin	Intact proinsulin/ C-peptide ratio	Split proinsulin	Split proinsulin/ C-peptide ratio
HOMA-IR index				
<i>Controls</i>	4.02 (0.66-7.36)	6.23 (1.41-11.06)	10.95 (3.22-18.17)	14.84 (3.99-25.70)
<i>Patients</i>	0.97 (-0.11-2.06)	0.43 (-0.86-1.71)	6.98 (3.44-10.52)	5.83 (1.40-10.25)
<i>P value*</i>	0.36	0.03	0.47	0.23
<i>RA on GC</i>	1.28 (-0.42-2.98)	0.39 (-1.66-2.44)	6.94 (3.38-10.50)	5.37 (1.06-9.69)
<i>RA non on GC</i>	0.74 (-0.82-2.28)	5.55 (-1.26-2.36)	4.95 (-1.29-11.18)	3.70 (-4.13-11.72)
<i>P value†</i>	0.63	0.90	0.57	0.72

P value represents the comparison of beta coefficient between controls and patients (*) and between RA on GC and RA non on GC (†) when interaction 'HOMAIR*disease' is included in the regression model.

HOMA-IR index is considered independent variable, and proinsulin metabolites are dependent variables.

References

1. Avina-Zubieta JA, Choi HK, Sadatsafavi M, Etminan M, Esdaile JM, Lacaille D. Risk of cardiovascular mortality in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a meta-analysis of observational studies. *Arthritis and rheumatism*. 2008 Dec 15; 59(12):1690-1697.
2. Meune C, Touze E, Trinquart L, Allanore Y. Trends in cardiovascular mortality in patients with rheumatoid arthritis over 50 years: a systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies. *Rheumatology (Oxford, England)*. 2009 Oct; 48(10):1309-1313.
3. Ferraz Amaro I, Diaz Gonzalez F, Gonzalez Juanatey C, Gonzalez Gay MA. [Insulin resistance and rheumatoid arthritis]. *Reumatologia clinica*. Mar-Apr; 7(2):124-129.
4. Wasko MC, Kay J, Hsia EC, Rahman MU. Diabetes mellitus and insulin resistance in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: risk reduction in a chronic inflammatory disease. *Arthritis care & research*. Apr; 63(4):512-521.
5. Gonzalez-Gay MA, Gonzalez-Juanatey C, Vazquez-Rodriguez TR, Miranda-Filloo JA, Llorca J. Insulin resistance in rheumatoid arthritis: the impact of the anti-TNF-alpha therapy. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. Apr; 1193:153-159.
6. Dessein PH, Stanwix AE, Joffe BI. Cardiovascular risk in rheumatoid arthritis versus osteoarthritis: acute phase response related decreased insulin sensitivity and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol as well as clustering of metabolic syndrome features in rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis research*. 2002; 4(5):R5.
7. Chung CP, Oeser A, Solus JF, Gebretsadik T, Shintani A, Avalos I, et al. Inflammation-associated insulin resistance: differential effects in rheumatoid arthritis and systemic lupus erythematosus define potential mechanisms. *Arthritis and rheumatism*. 2008 Jul; 58(7):2105-2112.

8. Moller DE, Flier JS. Insulin resistance--mechanisms, syndromes, and implications. *The New England journal of medicine*. 1991 Sep 26; 325(13):938-948.
9. Tilg H, Moschen AR. Inflammatory mechanisms in the regulation of insulin resistance. *Molecular medicine (Cambridge, Mass)*. 2008 Mar-Apr; 14(3-4):222-231.
10. O'Rahilly S, Gray H, Humphreys PJ, Krook A, Polonsky KS, White A, et al. Brief report: impaired processing of prohormones associated with abnormalities of glucose homeostasis and adrenal function. *The New England journal of medicine*. 1995 Nov 23; 333(21):1386-1390.
11. Kahn SE, Halban PA. Release of incompletely processed proinsulin is the cause of the disproportionate proinsulinemia of NIDDM. *Diabetes*. 1997 Nov; 46(11):1725-1732.
12. Roder ME, Dinesen B, Hartling SG, Houssa P, Vestergaard H, Sodoyez-Goffaux F, et al. Intact proinsulin and beta-cell function in lean and obese subjects with and without type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes care*. 1999 Apr; 22(4):609-614.
13. Aletaha D, Neogi T, Silman AJ, Funovits J, Felson DT, Bingham CO, 3rd, et al. 2010 rheumatoid arthritis classification criteria: an American College of Rheumatology/European League Against Rheumatism collaborative initiative. *Annals of the rheumatic diseases*. Sep; 69(9):1580-1588.
14. Prevoo ML, van 't Hof MA, Kuper HH, van Leeuwen MA, van de Putte LB, van Riel PL. Modified disease activity scores that include twenty-eight-joint counts. Development and validation in a prospective longitudinal study of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis and rheumatism*. 1995 Jan; 38(1):44-48.
15. Pincus T, Swearingen C, Wolfe F. Toward a multidimensional Health Assessment Questionnaire (MDHAQ): assessment of advanced activities of daily living and psychological status in the patient-friendly health assessment questionnaire format. *Arthritis and rheumatism*. 1999 Oct; 42(10):2220-2230.

16. Executive Summary of The Third Report of The National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, And Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol In Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III). *Jama*. 2001 May 16; 285(19):2486-2497.
17. Wallace TM, Levy JC, Matthews DR. Use and abuse of HOMA modeling. *Diabetes care*. 2004 Jun; 27(6):1487-1495.
18. Loopstra-Masters RC, Haffner SM, Lorenzo C, Wagenknecht LE, Hanley AJ. Proinsulin-to-C-peptide ratio versus proinsulin-to-insulin ratio in the prediction of incident diabetes: the Insulin Resistance Atherosclerosis Study (IRAS). *Diabetologia*. 2011 Dec; 54(12):3047-3054.
19. Oh JY, Barrett-Connor E, Wedick NM. Sex differences in the association between proinsulin and intact insulin with coronary heart disease in nondiabetic older adults: the Rancho Bernardo Study. *Circulation*. 2002 Mar 19; 105(11):1311-1316.
20. Haffner SM, Gonzalez C, Mykkanen L, Stern M. Total immunoreactive proinsulin, immunoreactive insulin and specific insulin in relation to conversion to NIDDM: the Mexico City Diabetes Study. *Diabetologia*. 1997 Jul; 40(7):830-837.
21. Bergman RN, Finegood DT, Kahn SE. The evolution of beta-cell dysfunction and insulin resistance in type 2 diabetes. *European journal of clinical investigation*. 2002 Jun; 32 Suppl 3:35-45.
22. Svenson KL, Lundqvist G, Wide L, Hallgren R. Impaired glucose handling in active rheumatoid arthritis: relationship to the secretion of insulin and counter-regulatory hormones. *Metabolism: clinical and experimental*. 1987 Oct; 36(10):940-943.
23. Matthews DR, Hosker JP, Rudenski AS, Naylor BA, Treacher DF, Turner RC. Homeostasis model assessment: insulin resistance and beta-cell function from fasting plasma glucose and insulin concentrations in man. *Diabetologia*. 1985 Jul; 28(7):412-419.

24. Dessein PH, Joffe BI. Insulin resistance and impaired beta cell function in rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis and rheumatism*. 2006 Sep; 54(9):2765-2775.
25. Dessein PH, Joffe BI, Stanwix A, Botha AS, Moomal Z. The acute phase response does not fully predict the presence of insulin resistance and dyslipidemia in inflammatory arthritis. *The Journal of rheumatology*. 2002 Mar; 29(3):462-466.
26. Chung CP, Oeser A, Solus JF, Avalos I, Gebretsadik T, Shintani A, et al. Prevalence of the metabolic syndrome is increased in rheumatoid arthritis and is associated with coronary atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis*. 2008 Feb; 196(2):756-763.
27. Hoes JN, van der Goes MC, van Raalte DH, van der Zijl NJ, den Uyl D, Lems WF, et al. Glucose tolerance, insulin sensitivity and beta-cell function in patients with rheumatoid arthritis treated with or without low-to-medium dose glucocorticoids. *Annals of the rheumatic diseases*. 2011 Nov; 70(11):1887-1894.
28. Giles JT, Allison M, Blumenthal RS, Post W, Gelber AC, Petri M, et al. Abdominal adiposity in rheumatoid arthritis: association with cardiometabolic risk factors and disease characteristics. *Arthritis and rheumatism*. 2010 Nov; 62(11):3173-3182.
29. Schacke H, Docke WD, Asadullah K. Mechanisms involved in the side effects of glucocorticoids. *Pharmacology & therapeutics*. 2002 Oct; 96(1):23-43.
30. Toms TE, Panoulas VF, Douglas KM, Griffiths HR, Kitas GD. Lack of association between glucocorticoid use and presence of the metabolic syndrome in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a cross-sectional study. *Arthritis research & therapy*. 2008; 10(6):R145.

Legend Figure 1.

Figure 1. Left graph (data plot on left axes) shows absolute values of intact proinsulin (black), split proinsulin (grey) and total insulin (white) in controls, non-on glucocorticoids rheumatoid arthritis patients (GC-RA), rheumatoid arthritis patients on glucocorticoids (GC+RA) and total rheumatoid arthritis patients (Total RA). Right graph (data plot on right axes) shows split roinsulin to C-peptide ratio (%) in the same groups. Significant p values are detailed.

Figure 1